

Workshop: The Inclusion of Technology and Sustainability in Engineering Education - a Realistic Approach

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Abstract

In the context of engineering education, it is mandatory to make students think about the impact that technology has on many aspects of life. We, as engineers, and our students as future engineers, must be aware of both the kind and detrimental effects of technology from the widest possible range of viewpoints. Issues such as the management of technological waste (related to planned obsolescence), the risk of generating unemployment caused using technology (automation and robotics), the relevance of having a strong technology industry to sustain our working environment, the relationship between sustainability and renewable resources..., are clear examples of aspects suitable for generating interesting debates. However, there is a key element that is usually left aside because it leads to uncomfortable conclusions: can we talk about sustainability without thinking about the effects of economic growth? In this hands-on session we will present an activity used to promote critical thinking in students about the relationship between technology, economic growth, and sustainability. We will try to present the most common thoughts when technology, energy, sustainability, and growth are put in the same container. In the workshop we will analyze whether or not sustainable development is compatible with economic growth and the consequences derived from this analysis.

Keywords: Active Learning in Engineering Education; Sustainability in Engineering Education; Critical Thinking in Engineering Education.

1 Introduction

We, as educators, expect engineering students to be aware of the future as a global issue. In fact, students explicitly want to discuss about ethic and sustainable development in engineering and engineering education, as conclude in the Board of European Students of Technology Symposium hold in Madrid in 2006 (BEST, 2006). Anyway, we can introduce elements closely related with the engineering framework to generate the appropriate working environment to think actively and critically about the future. The relationships of technology and sustainability, renewable energies and lifestyle, economic growth and ecologic waste management and, in general, the role of Engineers and Engineering in the consecution of a 'friendly' future are topics relevant enough to be taken into account in the engineering education process.

There is a real debate about whether the complexity of current problems is so great that a reliance on technical solutions alone is unrealistic. Nevertheless, the engineer in his or her professional role will still rely on applying technical solutions to problems such as energy provision and adaptation to climate change (Fenner et al. 2006). The problem is more complicated than it may appear at first sight, since, on the one hand, there are misconceptions in the relationship between sustainability and educational organizations (Ramírez, 2012) and, on the other hand, the concept of sustainable development of a high percentage of students is very superficial, limited to aspects such as recycling or Earth Hour (Sheikh et al. 2012). In addition, the conclusions obtained in a previous workshop (Romá & Martínez-Marín, 2016) showed that the simplified perception of the concept of sustainability is also supported by (some) engineering professors. Even some of them were reluctant to accept the information provided by scientific data to maintain their previous ideas.

The proposed activity is very similar to the one the author proposes to senior telecommunications engineering students in a session of a subject not focused on sustainability, as a way to introduce the topic in a curriculum without sustainability courses. The proposal presents two different levels. On the content side, we propose to discuss about sustainability, future, economic growth, technology, and the role of engineers in this puzzle. The second level of the activity will explore the effects of confronting one's mind scheme against facts that may (or may not) fit well in this structure. Usual reactions can be to deny the facts, re-interpret the facts to make them fit with the mind scheme so this scheme will be stronger or to make tremble the mind scheme. At first sight, the discussed questions may seem simple, but the pack formed by economy, environment and society is a very complex dynamic system. The fact that the system is dynamic is one of the key elements justifying the interest of making students think about these concepts. As stated in Booth-Sweenwy and Sterman (2000), highly educated subjects with extensive training in maths and science have poor understanding of some of the most basic system dynamics, because of some tests with students at the MIT Sloan School of Management.

2 Activities

There are many contributions analysing the factors affecting sustainability. The funny part is that it is possible to find the same factor considered as an element that will and will not ensure sustainability. Ecologists, economists, engineers, or scientists show very different points of view polarized by their academic profiles. For instance, while ecologists clearly rely on renewable energies as the key element for sustainability, (Cheng, 2015) clearly states that renewable energy will not be able to replace fossil fuels, and the work by Adair (2010) points out that the installation, operation, and maintenance of renewable plants needs fossil fuel questioning the sustainability of renewable energies. In this sense, the evolution (and future projection) of energy production is used as a key argument. Nowadays the energetic efficiency of renewable sources cannot be compared to that provided by fossil fuel.

Even general people without specific knowledge can also defend very different positions depending on their mind model. One of the most found positions is that based on the hope that technological improvements will be able to manage energy-related issues. In this sense, as pointed out in Tlusty, (2015) influencing people, as the General Electric CEO Jeffrey Immelt claimed that *for achieving sustainability, technology is the only answer*. A curious aspect highlighted in this work is that, in almost all the cases, when technology is apparently used with sustainability goals, the reality is that these technological improvements, under the tag of *restorative technologies*, their real mission is to reduce our impact on the planet caused by older technological developments.

The main goal of the session will be to explore the initial position regarding this topic and confront it with analytical information that can be easily handled from an engineering profile. It is recommended reading Nevel et al. (2024) (available online, the link is provided in the reference section).

To avoid the possibility of generating different ideas from those previously owned by the attendants to the proposed session, we will advance just an overview of the kind of activity that will be performed, as it is important to allow each participant to present his or her ideas about the topics presented. Moreover, as there are many possible different ideas, it is impossible to know in advance how the session will evolve. The attendees will be divided into small working groups. Basically, the session will consist of five stages:

1. Topic presentation. The complexity of sustainable development will be introduced.
2. Search for a consensus definition of sustainable development. In the academic literature, it has been estimated that there are over 300 definitions of sustainability and sustainable development (Jonston, P., Everad, M. & Santillo, D., 2007), so it is compulsory to state a unified starting point.

3. Each group will be assigned a dimension (population, energy, food, environment, economy, society) to analyze whether the definition of sustainable development is met as if they were independent variables, and to determine the role of technology in ensuring sustainability for the assigned dimension.
4. Confrontation of ideas with data. Information (real data) related to the exponential growth, economy and ecology will be presented.
5. Final thoughts.

The final part of the session will be used to conclude the key elements considered to be able to ensure sustainability and how these factors will affect to our future life. We will also analyse how these ideas can be fitted in our mind model. A parallelism with 'Psychohistory' (a fictional science in Isaac Asimov's "Foundation" book which combines history, sociology, and mathematical statistics) will be tried.

3 Expected results

As we are proposing a hands-on activity, its conclusion cannot be presented until the realization of the activity itself, so this section presents just as an outline, the main ideas we expect to debate. The starting point will necessarily be to share a definition of sustainable development.

We expect that, after the session, attendees will have a technically sounding vision of sustainability that may provoke some discomfort. We will discuss about the future from an economic point of view and the role of technology and energy to ensure a sustainable future. We will introduce the concept of economic growth in the equation and a discussion about economic growth and sustainability will follow (Higgins, 2013).

Due to the engineering profile of the attendees, the role of technology in the puzzle formed by society, economy, and environment can be used as an entrance to the sustainability problem.

We will explore if the initial mind model has or not been affected with the inclusion of new data. We will assess the interest of carrying this activity with attendees' students. We will study the possibility of exporting the idea of mind model confrontation to the attendees' areas.

4 References

- Adair, R. (2010). How sustainable is renewable energy? *Energy Bulletin*.
- Booth-Sweeney, L. & Sterman, J. D. (2000). Bathtub dynamics: initial results of a systems thinking inventory. *Systems dynamics review*, Vol. 16.
- Cheng, F. (2015). Renewable energy can't replace fossil fuels entirely. *The Straits Times*, Dec. 17, 2015.
- Fenner, R. A, Ainger C. M., Cruickshank, H. J. & Guthrie, P. M. (2006). Widening engineering horizons: addressing the complexity of sustainable development. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Engineering Sustainability 2006 159:4, 145-154
- Higgins, K. L. (2013). Economic growth and sustainability - are they mutually exclusive? Available on-line at <https://www.elsevier.com/connect/economic-growth-and-sustainability-are-they-mutually-exclusive> (last seen on may 2015).
- Jonston, P., Everad, M. & Santillo, D., 2007. Reclaiming the definition of sustainability. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 14(1):60-6.
- Nevel, A., Kling, A., Willamowski, R. & Schell, T. (2024). Recalibration of limits to growth: An update of the World3 model. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, Vol. 28-1 (feb 2024), 87-99.
Available online at <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/jiec.13442> (last seen on June 2024)
- Ramírez, G. A. (2012). Sustainable development: paradoxes, misunderstandings and learning organizations. *The Learning Organization*, Vol. 19 No. 1, 2012, 58-76.
- Romá, M., Martínez-Marín, T. (2016). What is the role of growth when talking about technology and sustainability?. Sustainability in Engineering Education. Proceedings of the PAEE/ALE conference. Guimaraes, Portugal, 2016, 10-13.
- Sheikh, S. N. S., Aziz, A. A., Yusof, K. M. (2012). Perception on Sustainable Development among New First Year Engineering Undergraduates. International Conference on Teaching and Learning in Higher Education in conjunction with Regional Conference on Engineering Education and Research in Higher Education, Volume 56, 2012, 530-536.
- Tlusty, M. (2015) Why sustainability requires more than technological advances. *Triple Pundit*, May 21, 2015.